

THE CONTENT OF TEACHING SPEAKING IN ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article presents ideas about the content of teaching speaking in English. It is explained that the content of the speech mainly includes linguistic, psychological and methodological aspects.

Keywords: linguistic, psychological, methodological, speech, teach

The content of teaching speaking in English comprises the following three aspects: Linguistic, Psychological and Methodological.

Linguistic Aspect consists of the language materials and speech materials, sentence structures, speech patterns and so on necessary for speaking. These materials must be selected on the base of certain topics. Besides, some extralinguist elements such as mime, actions and some other means must be kept in mind.

Psychological Aspect of speaking includes speech skills. That is reproduction, putting in the right place, transformation, extension, adding and mixing. Reproduction means reproducing of what he /she heard from the mouth of a teacher or recording.

Methodological Aspect includes the usage of methods, techniques of teaching speaking. It is important that pupils should use the means of basement. That is the means of listening, seeing, words and etc.

There are different situations that can because students dread speaking in the classroom, such as lacking vocabulary, worrying about their accent, and being frustrated about constructing the sentences with correct grammar. Many of them have all of these issues, so it seems natural that they have speaking difficulties. However, many have a good vocabulary and grammar grasps, but are still reluctant to speak. This may demonstrate that a good command of vocabulary and grammar is not enough.

Thus, we think in addition to constructing a positive learning environment to encourage them to speak more, emphasizing more on reading and writing are also critical. By improving their reading skills, they will develop a comparatively natural sense of English language, and by practicing writing, they are reinforcing or "memorizing" what they have learned about English. One may learn speaking very well without putting too much effort on reading and writing, but for most nonnative speakers who want to further pursue their education in the English context, they may need to consider improving them at the same time. For the speaking instructors, this can be a challenging task when integrating the teaching of other skills into the teaching of speaking.

Depending on the level of the students, there are manifold procedures and activities to involve and motivate students to speak in classroom situations such as linguistically structured activities, participation, observation and performance activities. Performance activities refer to activities in which learners, principally volunteers, are required to prime a speech and address it to the rest of the class. They take the form of describing a process or experiment, telling a story, talking about a personal experience, or delivering a formal lecture.

Like native speakers of English have to listen first and speak afterwards, ESL students do much the same - of course on a different level of learning capabilities. We think it's true that listening is the key to speaking. They even don't have to follow the listening materials all the time, since they are at least exposed to the sound of the language, the set of phonemes that is used by English speakers. Make them then speak by telling them that they can make every mistake possible and that the teacher won't interrupt them as long as (s)he understand the meaning of what they say. In cultures like Thailand, where people tend to avoid creating bad feelings by making mistakes, this is essential to have them speak some English.

Another important point is that they have to think in English if they want to sound naturally. When speaking, so they don't need to translate from L1 to ESL. There is of course not enough time to let them do this in class. Therefore, we work with them on using breaks and waiting periods outside

class to look around and describe what they see and feel for themselves without speaking - just thinking - or with speaking if they don't bother. Are there any pictures/graphics at the wall that they can describe? Do they stay outside and want to reflect on what they feel at the moment? Plans for later today, tomorrow? Even elementary level students have enough words available to think about those basic things. Try to initiate their ESL thinking and you ignite their speaking capabilities.

Students can improve English through songs- "language, that all may understand" we believe that the best way to improve speaking skills includes two aspects: first, they must read a lot in order to improve their vocabulary, and then, they must practice speaking. i.e. giving short lectures to their classmates.

We agree with many of the responses suggesting that confidence will increase as students have more opportunities to speak and succeed. We also agree that in some cultures or because of differences in personality, concerns about making mistakes may prohibit students' willingness to join in discussion in class. A way to safeguard against fear of speaking is to provide frequent opportunities for students to talk in small groups and/or with a partner before speaking before the larger group. Students will be more willing to talk with a supportive peer, practicing responses that will be useful for participation in the larger group later on during the class.

Cooperative game/word play would also be helpful, identifying or devising games that are appropriate for the age and stage of the language learners. So, for example, we might provide student pairs a set of word cards. One student (Partner 1) might provide clues so that Partner-2 might guess the correct word. This may force to use of question-asking, language elaboration, specific vocabulary recognition and naming. It has potential for increasing fluency, increase the speed of word-retrieval, and aid in direct processing-speaking in the target language. Another advantage to classroom management is that partners can be working simultaneously in different parts of the classroom. So, in a class of 20, with the potential for 10 student pairs, each pair will have significantly more opportunity for talking than when the instructor is attempting to address the entire class, with all participants forced into a sequential order of speaking, with 19 waiting while one speaks. This activity can be varied, dependent upon language level, with peer partners competing against the clock having a certain amount of time to "guess" all words; or competing against teams if competitiveness is associated with fun and a game-like atmosphere that does not spark increased fear of speaking.

It is very important to speak to your students in English most of the times. Of course, it is difficult to do this with a junior class, for example, there must be some instructions in the native language in order to be clear about the goals of a lesson or a grammar rule. However, it's true that the more you speak as a teacher in the foreign language the more the students get familiarized with this new language.

Regarding higher levels (e.g. B 2), role playing could really enhance students' oral skills. To do this, you'd rather motivate students to participate in the exercise engaging them at roles they adore these may be roles of athletes, actors, singers, heroes etc. Also, as already mentioned good solutions to improve their speaking and listening skills could be watching films with English subtitles which later on could be removed when students feel more confident to understand what they listen to. This should be done gradually in order to make them feel this is their choice and responsibility, something which stems from the fact that their "oral self-efficacy beliefs" got increased. Actually, we mustn't forget that first of all as educators we have to guide children in the learning process not to make all the decisions for the ways and the pace of learning instead of them.

Another constructive way to help students improve oral skills is let them talk in English via Skype in pairs or as a whole group as they would naturally do with their friends using their native language. They should talk about themselves, their interests, their school performance or their views about common themes, daily news and future plans. Furthermore, we suppose a useful idea would be reading books or magazines they like written in English and then trying to briefly narrate the stories in class and answer to questions asked by their classmates about the stories plot, main events, personality traits of the characters etc.

To improve a productive skill such as speaking you have to have them do just that - speak! How...by first giving them sufficient input on the topic/theme/situation, etc. This can be done using video clips, audio recordings, pictures, figurines and even simulations. You can progress from large groups to small group interaction and then when they are 'ready', individual orations can be encouraged.

For weaker classes we use prefabricated conversations that sound natural. They read the text aloud and ask their peers for any words they don't know. Then we have them have a conversation with the patterns read but using their own information. As long as we understand what they're saying we don't intervene with pronunciation. Why? If we taught cockneys, we'd have to intervene all the time.

Games such as "Simon says or Memory trees": "I went to the shop and I bought an apple". The next person says I went to the shop and bought an apple and adds what they bought, and so on where each person speaks. Or singing - some old folk songs, or current radio played songs. Or play a video clip and have them dialogue the situation - this also helps with learning emotional nuance.

We would like to make some comments on improving students' speaking skills. Making students speak more English in the classroom is not only a matter of "forcing" them to speak. This demands good preparation of proper material and implementation must be progressive and systematic which demands more teachers' workload. We mean lots of those teachers who learned what and how

to do in the classroom, as a teacher, simply don't do as they are supposed to. They seem as though they don't like to work much. No way! Teachers need to work much so they accomplish the teachers' role.

Pupils' speech in both forms may be of two kinds: prepared and unprepared. It is considered prepared when the pupil has been given time enough to think over its content and form. The pupils' speech is considered unprepared when, without any previous preparation, he can do the following: speak on a subject suggested by the teacher. Speak on the text read; speak on the text heard. Have an interview with a foreigner and etc.

It should be said that prepared and unprepared speech must be developed simultaneously from the very beginning. In the junior stage prepared speech takes the lead, while in the senior stage unprepared speech should prevail.

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